

Characterizing the influence of stress on foam conditioned sand for EPB tunneling

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ABSTRACT

To guarantee effective EPB TBM face support and performance, it is necessary to understand the mechanical behavior of foam-conditioned soil under realistic pressure conditions. This paper investigates the behavior of foam-conditioned soil under applied total pressures of up to 5 bar. The study examines the effect of total stress, effective stress, and key soil parameter void ratio on the behavior of foam-conditioned soil. Shear strength and compression tests were carried out in a field-portable pressurized test chamber on two granular soils with a variety of foam parameters. The results demonstrate that void ratio and effective stress are the main factors that influence the performance of foam-conditioned soil. It was determined that a certain ratio of void ratio to maximum void ratio was required to prevent the development of appreciable effective stress and, thus, high shear strength and low compressibility.

Keywords: EPB; soil conditioning; compressibility; shear strength

INTRODUCTION

Soil conditioning agents are used in earth pressure balance (EPB) tunneling to transform the excavated soil into a workable paste with the desired hydrological and mechanical properties. Reducing wear, power consumption, friction, adhesion, and improving the face stability and material flow are some of the benefits of using soil conditioning in EPB tunneling. Soil conditioning is performed by injecting foam, polymer, water, and bentonite to the tunnel face, excavation chamber and screw conveyor. The selection of conditioning agents mainly depends on soil type, geological condition (groundwater and soil permeability) and tunnel boring machine (TBM) features (injection points, open or closed cutterhead, type of foam generator, etc.). The most widely used soil conditioners are foamed surfactants and polymers, the latter of which is used for clay dispersion, anti-wear and water absorption (Milligan, 2000; Langmaack, 2000). Many studies have been performed on soil conditioning in granular soils, e.g. Vinai et al. 2007, Peila et al. 2007, Thewes & Budach, 2010, and others described in detail below. A thorough review of the experimental literature is provided in Budach & Thewes (2015).

Several methods have been proposed to estimate the foam volume V_F required to achieve the desired soil behavior. The first reference to void ratio/porosity in the determination of foam volume came from the work of Maidl (1995), who proposed that the necessary foam volume needed is that which fills the voids to the state where the coarse grains are not in contact, i.e., above the maximum porosity n_{max} of the coarse grain fraction (determined in his study per German standard DIN 18126 with

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fines removed). As shown in Equation (1), Maidl accounts for the formation water in the voids and the fine grained particles V_{200} in calculating V_F . Fine grained in Maidl's study included particles smaller than 0.075 mm. The latter assumes that the fines are void filling material for the coarse grained fraction and do not influence the soil behavior. Based on the assumption that the behavior of soil is governed by the soil's void content at $n > n_{max}$ and by the soil's coarse grains at $n < n_{max}$ (Kézdi, 1969), Maidl (1995) suggested a calculation method for the necessary foam volume V_F at chamber pressure, Equation (1). Here, n_{max} is the maximum porosity of the coarse grains in the soil (determined per German standard DIN 18126), V is the volume of the soil at n_{max} , V_{200} is the volume of fine grains in the soil, V_w is the volume of the water in the soil, and V_{ES} is the excavated soil volume. Budach (2012) showed that Equation (1) can lead to large differences in V_F for similar grain sizes. Furthermore, Maidl suggests that the necessary V_F is also influenced by foam deterioration, pore water replacement, and pressure changes that lead to foam compression and expansion.

$$V_F(\%) = \frac{n_{max}V - V_{200} - V_w}{V_{ES}} 100\% \quad (1)$$

Maidl and later Budach (2012) conducted pore air compression tests up to 4 bar on conditioned coarse-grained soils with no fines content and found that the conditioned soils follow the compression of air in the foam above n_{max} of the soil (per DIN 18126). They mixed soil with foam at atmospheric conditions and compressed the mix in a clear cylinder with compressed air. This set-up did not allow compression of the soil beyond its maximum porosity and, therefore, the influence of effective stress could not be taken into account.

The contractor Obayashi proposed an empirical relationship for foam volume as a percentage of excavated soil volume (Equation 2) based on the soil's coefficient of uniformity through a correction factor α , and the percentage of soil grains passing the No. 200 (0.075 mm), No. 40 (0.420 mm), and No. 10 (2.0 mm) sieves, represented by X , Y , and Z , respectively (Williamson et al., 1999). Williamson et al. state that Equation (2) is based on the assumption that the soil's grain size distribution needs to meet certain particle size criteria to be flowable and that deficient particle sizes in the grain size distribution of silty sands and gravely soils can be supplemented with foam. No mention is made of formation or chamber pressure; however, it is assumed that Equation (2) provides the appropriate V_F at chamber pressure.

$$V_F(\%) = \frac{\alpha}{2} [(60 - 4 X^{0.8}) + (80 - 3.3 Y^{0.8}) + (90 - 2.7 Z^{0.8})] \quad (2)$$

Bezuijen et al. (1999) showed that the porosity of the foam-conditioned sand in the excavation chamber has to be higher than the maximum porosity of the sand to reduce friction on the cutterhead. The authors implemented a lab test setup to investigate this hypothesis and to determine other foamed sand properties under more realistic pressure conditions than previous research (i.e., injection of foam, mixing of foam with soil, and removing of conditioned soil under applied vertical total stress). The authors compared the amount of foam necessary to achieve the desired soil behavior with and without water replacement. They found that more foam is needed if the water in the sand is replaced by foam. Their test results also show a relationship between the shear strength and the porosity of the foam-

conditioned sand. These and later tests (Bezuijen & Schaminée, 2001) indicate that the torque increases significantly when the porosity of the sample decreases towards the maximum porosity.

Houlsby & Psomas (2001), Psomas (2001), and Pena Duarte (2007) tested the compressibility of foam-conditioned sand under vertical total stress and found that it is stable (i.e., the foam bubbles do not collapse) at void ratios (e) higher than the sand's maximum void ratio (e_{max}) even under pressures up to 230 kPa (2.3 bar). The void ratio is the volumetric ratio of void content to solid content and is related to porosity as $e = n/(1-n)$. e_{max} is the void ratio resulting from the loosest placement of the soil in an oven-dried state, often determined via ASTM D 4253. Shear box tests showed that the linear trend between soil density and friction angle described by Bolton (1986) can be extended above the soil's maximum void ratio for foam-conditioned sand. Bolton's correlation states that the friction angle decreases linearly with increasing void ratio up to the void ratio at which a relative density of approximately 20% is reached and then remains constant up to e_{max} . The tests performed on conditioned sand showed that the friction angle never plateaus at $e < e_{max}$ and decreases further with increasing void ratio at $e > e_{max}$ approaching friction angles below 10° at $e/e_{max} > 2$.

EFNARC (2005) suggests soil-specific foam volume ranges at chamber pressure, reported as foam injection ratios FIR , which is another term for V_f , the volume ratio of foam to excavated soil. The suggested FIR s vary considerably for each soil type, e.g., 30-60% for sandy gravels. According to Thewes & Budach (2010), the EFNARC recommended FIR s are "roughly oriented" to the maximum void ratios of the different soil types.

Meng et al. (2011) used a pressurized vane shear apparatus to investigate the viscoplastic parameters, yield stress and viscosity, of conditioned sand under pressure. A vertical total stress of up to 4 bar was applied to the bottom surface of the conditioned soil sample through a gas bag placed inside the device. Their study showed that conditioned sand acts like a viscoplastic fluid with shear-thinning properties and that the viscoplastic parameters increase with increasing pressure and decrease with increasing FIR . The only parameters taken into account in this study were the FIR , the applied total pressure, and shear rate. The influence of effective stress or the sand's geotechnical properties on the viscoplastic parameters was not considered.

Bezuijen (2012) presents a theoretical calculation method for the foam consumption for EPB TBM tunneling. The approach is similar to Maidl's (1995), but adds the aspect of pore water replacement by foam and does not explicitly differentiate between total porosity and porosity of coarse grains only. Equation 3 yields the foam injection ratio FIR and takes the in-situ soil permeability k , the in-situ soil porosity n_s , a desired porosity in the excavation chamber n_m , which should be at or above the maximum porosity of the soil to limit grain stresses, the advance rate v_d , the tunnel radius R , and the piezometric head difference $\Delta\phi$ into account, Equation (3).

$$FIR = \frac{k\Delta\phi}{v_d R} - 1 + \frac{1-n_s}{1-n_m} \quad (3)$$

In summary, previous research has provided several empirical (Williamson et al., 1999; EFNARC, 2005) and theoretical (Maidl, 1995; Bezuijen, 2012) methods to determine the required foam volume. Although several researchers (Bezuijen et al., 1999; Bezuijen & Schaminée, 2001; Houlsby & Psomas, 2001; Psomas, 2001; Pena Duarte, 2007; Meng et al., 2011) investigated the influence of foam volume

and/or void ratio on the behavior of foam-conditioned soil under applied total pressure, none of the studies took the influence of effective stress or pore pressure on the soil behavior into account. Furthermore, the studies mainly focused on the soil behavior at $e > e_{max}$, and the behavior of conditioned soil transitioning from $e > e_{max}$ to $e < e_{max}$, where effective stress starts to develop, has not yet been investigated.

The purpose of the performed study is to further the research of Maidl (1995) and Bezuijen et al. (1999) that first recognized the importance of void ratio on the behavior of foam-conditioned soil. In contrast to previous research, this study will examine and explain the conditioned soil behavior in the context of effective stress. A simple and field-portable testing method for measuring foam-conditioned soil behavior of soils transitioning from $e > e_{max}$ to $e < e_{max}$ is introduced. Two types of tests were performed in a pressurized testing chamber to analyze the influence of total and effective stress and the key soil property void ratio on the vane shear strength and compression of two conditioned sands. A total pressure was applied mechanically to allow pore pressure and effective stress to form freely in the sample.

BACKGROUND

Surfactant-based foam and polymers are the main conditioning agents used in EPB TBM tunneling to improve excavated soil behavior. Soil conditioners in general are supposed to decrease the in-situ soil's permeability, decrease friction, and, therefore, increase the soil's flowability, and reduce machine torque and energy consumption. Since this paper only discusses the effects of foam on soil behavior, the following section focus on foam conditioning parameters only. Furthermore, due to a lack of clarity in defining industry-standard foam terms in the literature, the pressure-dependent nature of foam conditioning parameters is emphasized via notation.

Surfactant concentration C_f is the volumetric fraction of surfactant in the water-surfactant or foam solution, Equation (4). The foam expansion ratio (FER_p) is the volumetric fraction of produced foam to the used surfactant solution, Equation (5). The foam injection ratio (FIR_p) is the volumetric fraction of injected foam to excavated soil, often represented as a percentage, Equation (6). Both FER_p and FIR_p are strongly influenced by air pressure as described below, and are therefore designated with a subscript p (bar) reflective of the desired chamber gage pressure (atmospheric pressure = 0 bar gage pressure and the subscript 0 is used).

$$C_f = \frac{V_{Sf}}{V_{Sf} + V_W} = \frac{V_{Sf}}{V_L} 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$FER_p = \frac{V_{F,p}}{V_L} = \frac{V_L + V_{A,p}}{V_L} = 1 + \frac{V_{A,p}}{V_L} \quad (5)$$

$$FIR_p = \frac{V_{F,p}}{V_{ES}} 100 = \frac{V_L + V_{A,p}}{V_{ES}} 100\% \quad (6)$$

where V_{Sf} is the volume of surfactant, V_W is the volume of water, V_L is the volume of surfactant solution, $V_{F,p}$ is the foam volume, $V_{A,p}$ is the volume of air, and V_{ES} is the volume of excavated soil. The only value with a certain degree of ambiguity in these equations is the volume of excavated soil. While it is determined by the excavation diameter and the thrust jack stroke in EPB TBMs, it has to be carefully

defined for lab tests. Therefore, it is best to calculate the dry soil mass needed to achieve the desired volume with in-situ density and water content, if these parameters are known.

A relationship between pore air pressure and the conditioning parameters FER_p and FIR_p can be formulated based on Boyle's gas law. Stemming from the ideal gas law, Boyle's law states that the volume and pressure of an ideal gas at constant temperature are inversely related as described in Equation (7). Combining Equation (7) and Equation (5) results in the theoretical FER_p , see Equation (8). Combining Equation (5) and Equation (6) provides the relationship between FER_p and FIR_p at two different pressures, Equation (9).

$$V_{A,p} = V_{A,0} \frac{p_{atm}}{p + p_{atm}} \quad (7)$$

$$FER_p = 1 + \frac{V_{A,0}}{V_L} \frac{p_{atm}}{p + p_{atm}} = 1 + (FER_0 - 1) \frac{p_{atm}}{p + p_{atm}} \quad (8)$$

$$FIR_p = FIR_0 \frac{FER_p}{FER_0} \quad (9)$$

Here, $V_{A,p}$ is the theoretical volume of air, $V_{A,0}$ is the volume of air at atmospheric pressure, p_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure in terms of total pressure, FER_p is the theoretical FER, and FIR_p is the foam injection ratio. Figure 1 shows the theoretical relationship between pressure and the conditioning parameters FER_p and FIR_p according to Boyle's gas law.

Figure 1. Theoretical relationship between pressure and foam expansion ratio (FER) and foam injection ratio (FIR) according to Boyle's gas law

It has been assumed that conditioned soil has ideal properties for EPB tunneling above its maximum void ratio/porosity (Bezuijen et al., 1999; Maidl, 1995). Above its maximum void ratio, the

soil's grains are nominally in contact with each other and low levels of effective stress are present in the soil. The necessary FIR_p to reach this porosity can be calculated from the in-situ soil's density, water content, specific gravity, and maximum void ratio/porosity. Since the conditioned soil is under pressure in the excavation chamber, the desired FIR has to be achieved under the fluid pressure conditions present in the chamber. The void ratio and FIR are directly related and Equations (10) through (12) display the derivation of the minimum FIR under pressure.

$$n = \frac{V_V}{V_{ES}} = 1 - \frac{\rho}{(1+w)G_S} \quad (10)$$

$$e_{max} = \frac{V_{V,max}}{V_s} = \frac{FIR_p V_{ES} + \alpha V_w}{(1-n)V_{ES}} = \frac{FIR_p V_{ES} + \alpha w V_s G_S}{(1-n)V_{ES}} \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{FIR_p V_{ES} + \alpha w (1-n)V_{ES} G_S}{(1-n)V_{ES}} = \frac{FIR_p + \alpha w (1-n)G_S}{1-n}$$

$$FIR_p = (1-n)(e_{max} - \alpha w G_S) \cdot 100\% \quad (12)$$

where n is the porosity, V_V is the volume of voids, V_{ES} is the total volume, ρ is the total density, w is the water content, and G_S is the specific gravity, all of the in-situ yet to be excavated soil. e_{max} is the maximum void ratio per ASTM D4254, $V_{V,max}$ is the volume of voids at e_{max} , V_s is the volume of soil solids, and V_w is the volume of pore water. The pore water replacement factor α indicates the percentage of pore water that is replaced by foam. If the pore water is completely replaced with foam ($V_w = 0$) then $\alpha = 0$ and if no pore water is replaced then $\alpha = 1$. In reality the pore water will be replaced depending on the hydraulic conductivity of the soil and the foam injection pressure (Bezuijen, 2012). Figure 2 shows an example of how volumes can change from its in-situ state to its state after foam injection at pressure to when it exits the screw conveyor at atmospheric pressure. The analysis assumes that the foam remains stable and mixed with the soil.

Figure 2. Volumetric difference between in-situ soil, conditioned soil with a $FIR_p = 40\%$, and conditioned soil with $FIR_0 = 120\%$

TEST METHODS AND PLAN

Two different types of tests were performed to investigate the effect of pressure and geotechnical properties on the behavior of foam-conditioned soil. The first test analyzes the compression behavior and the second test analyzes the vane shear strength of foam-conditioned soil. The foam used for the tests was produced with an in-house developed foam generator (see Figure 3). The laboratory foam generator mimics the air, surfactant solution and foam velocities observed in TBM scale foam generators, and at the line pressures observed in TBM scale systems (Mooney et al. 2017). The foam generator can regulate and measure gage pressures and flow rates of the pressurized air and surfactant solution used to produce the foam. The air flow rate is measured with a mass flow meter and, therefore, provides the flow rate at atmospheric pressure. Thus, the foam generator is able to generate foam with the desired FER_0 (at atmospheric pressure).

- a. PC (system controller)
- b. data acquisition
- c. liquid flow regulator
- d. air pressure regulator
- e. air/fluid mixing chamber
- f. pressure transducer
- g. air mass flow meter
- h. backflow collector
- i. conditioning agent storage tank

Figure 3. Laboratory foam generator used to produce the foam for the tests

The testing device used for both types of tests was also developed in-house, see Figure 4. It is a pressurized testing chamber that can mechanically apply up to 5 bar of vertical total stress to a soil or conditioned soil sample under radially confined conditions (zero lateral strain). The vertical total stress is applied through a compression spring assembly that also serves as a means of force measurement. The device does not require power or a pressurized air supply for operation. It is therefore portable and can be used for in-field measurements. The testing device consists of several parts including a chamber, rods, a top platen, a compression spring, and a reaction plate. Two types of top platens are used for the tests. The top platen for the compression test is a solid aluminum plate with a port and valve to release air from the chamber during platen seating. The platen used for the vane shear test additionally has a circular opening for the shear vane shaft. The pressure chamber has an inner diameter of 156 mm and a height of 229 mm. The total vertical stress σ_{vt} on top of the soil sample can be calculated using the spring constant, spring deformation, and the cross-sectional area of the soil sample, Equation (13). The vertical effective stress σ'_{vt} at the top of the sample can be calculated from the total vertical stress σ_{vt} and the pore pressure u that is measured through the port in the top platen, Equation (14).

$$\sigma_{vt} = \frac{(H_{S0} - H_{Si}) k_{sp} - F_f}{A} \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma'_{vt} = \sigma_{vt} - u \quad (14)$$

where H_{S0} is the original height of the compression spring, H_{Si} is the height of the compression spring at the i -th compression step, k_{sp} is the steel spring constant, F_f is the frictional force between the side walls of the chamber and the top platen, and A is the cross-sectional area of the soil in the chamber. The frictional force F_f was determined by performing a compression test on air and comparing the measured pore pressure to the pressure indicated by the spring compression. It should be noted that the side friction between the chamber wall and the soil sample and, therefore, the change in total vertical stress with depth is unknown. Thus, a non-uniform stress state of the sample in the testing chamber is possible, and likely when $e < e_{max}$ and sidewall interface friction develops.

Figure 4. Pressurized Testing Chamber (PTC) with dimensions in mm

A certain compressibility of the material in the excavation chamber is desired to allow for a better control of the support pressure (Maidl, 1995; Budach, 2012). The necessary compressibility depends on the advance rate, the geometry of the TBM, the reaction time of the system, and the maximum allowed pressure change. Budach calculated the necessary (minimum) load and unload compressibility for a specific TBM to be 1.3% and 1.9%, respectively, for a maximum allowed pressure change of 0.5 bar and a reaction time of 15 seconds (i.e., 2.6 %/bar and 3.8 %/bar, respectively). The compressibility C of the foam-conditioned soil can be calculated with Equation (15) and takes the original sample volume $V_{T,0}$, the change in sample volume $\Delta V_{T,p}$, and the change in total vertical stress $\Delta\sigma_{vt}$ into account.

$$C = \frac{1}{V_{T,0}} \frac{\Delta V_{T,p}}{\Delta\sigma_{vt}} \cdot 100\% \quad (15)$$

A 70 mm x 70 mm shear vane is used to measure the shear strength of the foam-conditioned soil in the testing chamber. The vane shear strength τ_v is estimated according to ASTM D2573 from the torque measured by a torque wrench and the vane dimensions and can be simplified for vanes with height equal to diameter, Equation (16).

$$\tau_v = \frac{T}{\pi d_v^2 \left(\frac{h_v}{2} + \frac{d_v}{6} \right)} = \frac{6T}{4\pi d_v^3} \quad (16)$$

where T is the measured torque, d_v is the diameter of the vane, and h_v is the height of the vane. Because the shear stress is also dependent on the shear rate, a constant low rotation speed of approximately 1 rpm was used for all vane shear tests.

Two sands were used for both types of tests. Their geotechnical properties are presented in Table 1 and their grain size distributions are shown in Figure 5. One type of conditioning agent, a general surfactant typically used on cohesionless soils, was used for all tests with both soils. The C_f and FER_0 were kept the same for all tests, while three different FIR_0 values were used (the same three FIR s for both soils). The conditioning parameters used in both types of tests for both soils are presented in Table 2. Using Equations (10) and (12) we can calculate the necessary FIR_p to reach e_{max} for each soil. Soil 1 requires a minimum $FIR_p = 24\%$ and soil 2 requires a minimum $FIR_p = 38\%$. The conditioned soil sample preparation for each test are discussed in the following sections and the specific testing procedures for the tests including calculations can be found in the Appendix.

Table 1. Geotechnical properties of Soil 1 and Soil 2

	Soil 1	Soil 2
Soil type	Poorly graded sand	Poorly graded sand
Gravel (%)	1	6
Sand (%)	88	92
Coarse Sand (%)	6	4
Medium Sand (%)	56	55
Fine Sand (%)	26	33
Silt (%)	9	2
Clay (%)	2	0
Plasticity Index	non plastic	non plastic
Moist In-Situ Density (g/cm^3)	2.12	1.88
Water Content, w (%)	10	10
Specific Gravity, G_s	2.65	2.66
e_{max}	0.59	0.86
D_{50} (mm)	0.63	0.66

Figure 5. Grain size distributions of the two sand soils, soil 1 and soil 2, used for the tests

Table 1. Surfactant and soil conditioning parameters used in both types of tests and for both soils.

Parameter	Value
Surfactant Type	BASF SLF 47
Surfactant Concentration, C_f (%)	5
Surfactant Solution Density, ρ_L (g/cm ³)	1.08
Foam Expansion Ratio, FER_0 (-)	10
Foam Injection Ratio, FIR_0 (%)	30, 50, 70

Soil Preparation

Water is added to air dried soil in a mixing container to bring it to the desired water content. The desired water content is normally the in-situ water content of the soil at a particular site. In this study, the use of 10% is a reasonable but arbitrary value for in-situ conditions because we are not simulating conditions at a particular site. While the influence of water content on conditioned soil is not the focus of this study, it is clear from Equations 1 and 10 that the in-situ water content influences the required foam.

A larger than necessary amount of foam with the desired C_f and FER_0 is produced with the lab foam generator. The FER_0 measured by the foam generator is confirmed by weighing part of the foam in a container with known weight and volume. Using the container volume, the measured mass of foam, and the surfactant density in Equation (5), the FER_0 of the produced foam can be calculated, see Equation (17). Only FER_0 s within ± 1 of the desired FER_0 were accepted for the tests. The foam is added to the soil to attain the desired FIR_0 . The FIR_0 is a volumetric measurement but since mass measurements are more accurate than volume measurements in the case of foam and soil, the necessary mass of foam is calculated using Equation (18) and (19). The required mass of foam is then added to the soil mixing container. The soil and foam are mixed by hand at atmospheric conditions until a homogeneous consistency is reached.

$$FER_0 = \frac{V_{F,0} \rho_L}{m_F} \quad (17)$$

$$FIR_0 = \frac{V_{F,0}}{V_{ES}} \cdot 100 = \frac{\rho_S V_L FER_0}{m_{ES}} \cdot 100 = \frac{\rho_S m_L FER_0}{m_{ES} \rho_L} \cdot 100 \quad (18)$$

$$m_F = m_L = \frac{FIR_0 m_{ES} \rho_L}{FER_0 \rho_S \cdot 100} \quad (19)$$

where $V_{F,0}$ is the volume of foam, ρ_L is the density of the surfactant solution, m_F is the mass of foam, ρ_{ES} is the moist in-situ density of soil, m_{ES} is the mass of moist soil, and m_L is the mass of surfactant solution. The process of producing foam and mixing the foam with the soil is time sensitive due to the instability of foam at atmospheric conditions and should be completed fast. Moreover, during the process of mixing soil and foam at atmospheric conditions foam bubbles can be destroyed, reducing the FER_0 and

FIR_0 , or more air can be incorporated into the mix, increasing the FER_0 and FIR_0 . Therefore, the actual FER_0 and FIR_0 often deviate from their desired target values and should be calculated from the achieved total volume before the start of the test.

RESULTS

The following sections present the results from compression and vane shear tests performed on the two soils. For each soil and type of test, three FIR_0 samples were prepared and tested (target $FIR_0 = 30, 50$ and 70%). The measured FIR_0 deviated from the target values due to mixing at atmospheric conditions and are presented for each test. Each sample was uniaxially compressed to total vertical stress σ_{vt} approaching 5 bar (500 kPa).

Compression Test Results

Figure 6 presents a comparison of several compression test results of soil 1. Higher FIR_0 samples naturally begin with higher initial void ratios and exhibit greater compressibility. The lower the FIR_0 the lower the total vertical stress at which the sample reaches e_{max} . The void ratio begins to deviate from the 'air-governed' void ratio (solid lines) at a transitional e/e_{max} ratio of around 1.2 for all three samples. The air-governed void ratio is the void ratio due to air compression according to Boyle's law assuming soil compressibility is governed by the contained air only, using the total vertical stress as a measure of pore pressure. The pore pressure increases at a rate similar to the total vertical stress until the transitional e/e_{max} ratio is reached. The vertical effective stress begins to develop thereafter. The sample with the lowest FIR_0 develops little pore pressure because its initial e/e_{max} ratio is below the transitional ratio of 1.2. Vertical effective stress therefore develops from the beginning of the test. This result indicates that conditioned soil compression above the transitional e/e_{max} ratio is air compression due to increasing pore pressure but that grain-to-grain stresses govern the behavior below this ratio. During the unloading stage (unfilled symbols) the samples only begin to expand when little effective stress is left (i.e., pore pressure \approx total stress). This suggests that the compression can only decrease with the pore pressure when little effective stress is acting on the sample. Each of the three samples experience fully elastic behavior, i.e., full recovery of vertical strain upon unloading.

Figure 6. Compression results of soil 1. Compression δ (a), void ratio e (b), pore pressure u (c), and vertical effective stress σ'_{vt} (d) plotted against the total vertical stress σ_{vt} . Filled markers represent loading, unfilled markers represent unloading, and solid lines represent the air-governed void ratio

The results can also be presented as compressibility values (Equation 15) plotted against the total and effective vertical stress as shown in Figure 7. Figure 7 shows that the compressibility decreases with

increasing total and effective vertical stress. For the $FIR_0 = 70\%$ sample, the compressibility is close to the air-governed compressibility (solid lines) at low total vertical stresses. With increasing total vertical stress, when effective stress starts to develop, the compressibility starts to deviate from this air-governed compressibility. For the $FIR_0 = 27\%$ sample, the vertical effective stress develops from the onset of loading and the compressibility is well below the air-governed compressibility. Values of compressibility range from 10 - 50%/bar in the air-governed regime above $e/e_{max} = 1.2$ and range from 0.3 - 10%/bar below $e/e_{max} = 1.2$. When the compressibility of the $FIR_0 = 70\%$ sample is plotted against the total vertical stress, it is generally higher than the compressibility of the other two samples. When plotted against vertical effective stress, however, compressibility is similar for all three samples, confirming that the particle interaction is governing the overall compressibility in this region and dominates any subtle influence that pore pressure has.

Figure 7. Compressibility of soil 1 with different FIR_0 plotted against total and effective vertical pressure. Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil and solid lines represent the air-governed compressibility

Figure 8 presents the results of several compression tests performed on soil 2. Similar to soil 1, the initial void ratio and the total vertical stress at which the maximum void ratio is reached increases with FIR_0 . The void ratio starts to deviate from the air-governed void ratio (solid lines) at a transitional e/e_{max} ratio of around 1.2, which is the same transitional ratio as for soil 1. However, the FIR_p necessary to reach this e/e_{max} ratio is higher for soil 2, since soil 2 has a lower fine content and, therefore, a higher e_{max} than soil 1. The pore pressure increases at a rate similar to the total vertical stress until the transitional e/e_{max} ratio is reached and the effective stress starts to develop. This indicates that the compression is mainly due to pore air compression above this transitional ratio and starts to be governed by grain stresses below this transitional ratio. During the unloading stage the samples only begin to expand when little effective stress is left (i.e., pore pressure \approx total stress). This suggests that the compression can only decrease with the pore pressure when little effective stress is acting on the sample.

Figure 8. Compression results of soil 2. Compression δ (a), void ratio e (b), pore pressure u (c), and vertical effective stress σ'_{vt} (d) plotted against the total vertical stress σ_{vt} . Filled markers represent loading, unfilled markers represent unloading, and solid lines represent the air-governed void ratio realized if the soil would be governed by the contained air only

The results are also presented as compressibility values plotted against the total and effective vertical stress in Figure 9. The figure shows that the compressibility decreases with increasing total and effective stress. At lower total stresses the compressibility of the two samples with high FIR_0 is close to the air-governed compressibility (solid lines) realized if the soil would be governed by the contained air only. When effective stresses start to develop the compressibility starts to deviate from the air-governed compressibility. The compressibility at negligible effective stresses varies from 10 - 50 %/bar and seems to be mainly dictated by the air volume contained in the sample. After effective stress develops it seems to be the main factor that influences the compressibility.

Figure 9. Compressibility of soil 2 with different FIR_0 plotted against total and effective vertical pressure. Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil and solid lines represent the air-governed compressibility

Figure 10 shows the compressibility of both soils plotted against the void ratio. The compressibility below e_{max} is below 2.5 %/bar for soil 1 and below 2.0 %/bar for soil 2. According to Budach (2012), a compressibility around 3.8 %/bar is sufficient for a metro sized EPB TBM. For soil 1 and soil 2 this would place the necessary void ratio just above e_{max} , but still below the transitional e/e_{max} ratio of 1.2. This indicates that for these soils the necessary compressibility can be achieved even at void ratios that result in grain-to-grain stresses. The relationship between the void ratio and the compressibility is apparent and appears to be almost linear for both soils.

Figure 10. Compressibility plotted against void ratio for both soils and different FIR_0 s. Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil

Vane Shear Test Results

Figure 11 shows a comparison of several vane shear test results for both soils. A separate batch of foam-conditioned soil samples was prepared for the vane shear tests and due to mixing at atmospheric pressure the achieved FIR_0 are different than the target FIR_0 and the compression test FIR_0 . For both soils the vane shear strength does not significantly develop until vertical effective stress initiates. The data also indicates a linear relationship between the vane shear strength and the effective vertical stress consistent with Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion (Figure 11b and 11d). The transition from $e > e_{max}$ to $e < e_{max}$ (unfilled to filled markers) has an influence on the development of vane shear strength and effective stress.

Figure 11. Vane shear strength plotted against vertical stress for soil 1 (a and b) and soil 2 (c and d). Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil

Plotting the vane shear strength against the void ratio clearly shows the relationship to each other, as shown in Figure 12. For $e > e_{max}$, the vane shear strength remains at low levels. For both soils the maximum vane shear strength at $e > e_{max}$ is around 20 kPa, but mainly remains below 10 kPa for high void ratios. It starts to increase at a certain transitional void ratio and then increases significantly at $e < e_{max}$. This transitional void ratio is around 0.7 for soil 1 and 1.0 for soil 2 at an e/e_{max} ratio of 1.2 for both soils. The relationship between vane shear strength and void ratio for $e < e_{max}$ seems to be almost linear. However, this linearity mainly depends on the effective stress in the sample as shown in Figure 11 and can, therefore, change from sample to sample depending on the developed effective stress. It should also be noted that a certain error in the calculation of the void ratio can be expected due to error propagation in the calculation and a probable heterogeneity of the sample during the test.

Figure 12. Vane shear strength plotted against void ratio for soil 1 (a) and soil 2 (b). Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Two granular soils were conditioned with foam and their compression behavior and vane shear strength was determined experimentally under total applied pressure. The results show that effective stress starts to develop below a transitional e/e_{max} ratio, which was found to be 1.2 for both of the tested soils. Above this transitional void ratio the soil is governed by the contained air, and below e_{max} it is governed by grain-to-grain stresses. This indicates that the soil has a zone in which it transitions from air-governed to governed by grain-to-grain stresses alone. Although both soils start to transition at the same e/e_{max} ratio, the foam required to reach this transitional ratio is higher for soil 2 than for soil 1. Soil 2 contains more gravel and less fines than soil 1 and has, and therefore, a higher e_{max} than soil 1. This explains the greater amount of foam necessary to achieve the desired e/e_{max} ratio.

The compressibility above the transitional e/e_{max} ratio is mostly above 10%/bar for both soils, which is well above the minimum 3.8%/bar suggested for a metro-sized EPB TBM (Budach, 2012). In the transition zone between $e/e_{max} = 1.2$ and $e/e_{max} = 1.0$ the compressibility decreases below the desired value even before e_{max} is reached. The vane shear strength above the transitional e/e_{max} ratio is below 10 kPa and only increases up to 20 kPa in the transitional zone. Furthermore, the vane shear strength follows the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion and increases with increasing effective stress. These results indicate that to guarantee a high enough compressibility and negligible vane shear strength, enough foam needs to be added to increase the soil's void ratio not only above e_{max} , as suggested by Maidl (1995) and Bezuijen (2012), but above the transitional e/e_{max} ratio.

The results of the performed study can be summarized in the following points:

- FIR_0 and FER_0 change when mixed with soil at atmospheric pressure, which makes the reproducibility of the performed study challenging.
- FIR_p and void ratio are directly related (i.e., if a value changes with void ratio it also changes with FIR).

- Effective stress only significantly develops in the tested foam-conditioned sands below a certain transitional e/e_{max} ratio. The transitional e/e_{max} ratio was around 1.2 for both soils.
- The compressibility of the foam-conditioned soil is governed by compressibility of the contained air above the transitional e/e_{max} ratio.
- The compressibility is governed by the effective stress and the soil's compressibility below the transitional e/e_{max} ratio.
- The vane shear strength increases with increasing effective stress according to the Mohr-Coulomb criterion.
- Since effective stress does not significantly develop above the transitional e/e_{max} ratio, the vane shear strength is very low for these void ratios.

The results of this study can be directly applied to soil conditioning practice. With the information provided from a geotechnical investigation and understanding the anticipated pressures of a specific project, the proposed foam volume required to properly condition soil can be estimated using the equations provided above and considering the transitional void ratio. To verify, soil samples can be conditioned at these proposed levels, pressurized to anticipated in-situ conditions in a pressurize chamber like the one described herein, and tested for shear strength (torque), compressibility and other mechanical parameters as desired. The testing allows for verification and adjustment of the soil conditioning parameters such that the recipe is effective under pressures that exist at the tunnel face and chamber.

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APPENDIX

The Appendix presents a detailed description of the test implementation of both the compression and vane shear test as well as equations for all calculated parameters that are not introduced in the main part of the paper.

Compression Test

For the one-dimensional compression test, the soil mixture is placed in the chamber, the top is leveled, and wetted filter paper is placed on top of the soil. The top platen with the air release port opened is slid into the chamber until it touches the top of the soil, which is normally indicated by liquid filling the air release port. A pore pressure sensor can then be connected to the air release port in the top platen. Otherwise the air release port is closed. Each test is performed under undrained conditions, i.e., drainage is not allowed. Then the depth of the top platen from the top of the chamber side wall is measured at two opposing points. This determines the original height and volume of the soil sample in the chamber. Next the compression spring is placed and centered on the top platen. The reaction plate is slid onto the ACME rods and leveled on top of the spring with the help of four nuts screwed onto the rods and two bull's eye levels attached to the plate. The distance from the bottom of the reaction plate to the top platen and to the side walls of the chamber is measured with a depth gauge through the two slits in the reaction plate. These distances determine the height of the soil sample with the top assembly attached as well as the compression of the spring due to leveling. Vertical pressure is applied to the top of the soil sample by tightening the nuts on the rods that lowers the reaction plate and compresses the spring. The bull's eye levels are used to keep the reaction plate level. After each step of compression, the distance between the reaction plate and the top platen and the side wall is measured through the two slits in the reaction plate. This provides the height of the sample and spring compression at each step. A pore pressure reading is also taken at every step. When the desired maximum total stress level is reached, the unloading cycle can be started by loosening the nuts on the rods, leveling the reaction plate, and measuring the distances in steps as during the load cycle. The pore pressure measurement is again taken at every step.

Vane Shear Test

The vane shear test is performed similarly to the compression test. The only difference is the shear vane placed in the soil and the special top platen used. The shear vane is vertically centered in the soil sample. If the pore pressure is measured during the test a filter paper with a hole to fit over the shear vane shaft is wetted and placed on the soil. The top platen with the center hole is slid onto the shear vane shaft and into the chamber until liquid can be seen in the air release hole. The air release hole is either closed or the pore pressure sensor is connected. The depth of the top platen from the top of the chamber side wall is measured. The top assembly with spring and reaction plate is attached in the same way as for the compression test. The spring is set centered on the top plate around the vane shear shaft. The reaction plate is placed on top with the vane shear shaft going through its center hole. The shear vane should be pulled upwards so it is not in contact with the bottom of the chamber and has enough room on the bottom to allow for downward movement of the top platen during the soil compression. The reaction plate is then leveled. In addition to the distance and pressure measurements, which are taken in the same manner as during the compression test, the torque required to turn the shear vane is measured with a torque wrench at each step. The height of the shear vane shaft over the reaction plate

should be measured at each step to assure the vane is not in contact with the bottom of the chamber or the top platen. The torque measurement is only valid when the vane does not touch the chamber and there is enough space for the largest particles in between the vane and the chamber.

PTC Calculations

Several parameters can be calculated from the measurements taken during the tests. Actual compression and theoretical compression of air according to Boyle's law can be calculated for each step during the test, Equations (A.1) and (A.4). The latter uses the volume of air in the chamber at the beginning of the test, Equation (A.3), and the applied total vertical stress as a measure of pore pressure to calculate the theoretical compression. The porosity and void ratio can also be calculated for each step, Equations (A.5) and (A.6). By replacing the actual compression with the theoretical compression in the equations, the theoretical porosity and void ratio can be calculated.

$$\delta_p = H_{S,p} - H_{W,p} - d_0 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$V_{T,p} = (H_{PTC} - d_0 - t - \delta_p)A \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$V_{A,p} = V_{T,p} - V_S - V_w - V_L = V_{T,p} - \frac{m_d}{G_S} - V_w - V_L \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\delta_{A,p} = \frac{V_{A,0}}{A} \left(1 - \frac{p_{atm}}{p + p_{atm}} \right) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$n_p = \frac{V_V}{V_{T,p}} = 1 - \frac{V_S}{V_{T,p}} = 1 - \frac{m_d}{G_S V_{T,p}} = 1 - \frac{m_d}{G_S (V_{T,0} - \delta_p A)} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$e_p = \frac{n_p}{1 - n_p} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

δ_p is the sample compression, $H_{S,p}$ is the distance between the reaction plate and the top platen, $H_{W,p}$ is the distance between the reaction plate and the side wall of the chamber, and d_0 is the initial depth of the lid. $V_{T,p}$ is the total sample volume in the chamber, H_{PTC} is the internal height of the chamber, t is the top platen thickness, and A is the cross-sectional area of the sample. $V_{A,p}$ is the volume of air, V_S is the volume of soil grains, V_w is the volume of water, V_L is the volume of solution, m_d is the mass of dry soil, and G_S is the specific gravity, all in respect to the material in the chamber. $\delta_{A,p}$ is the compression of air according to Boyle's ideal gas law, p_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure, and p is the measured gage pressure. n_p is the porosity, V_V is the volume of voids, and e_p is the void ratio. The subscript p indicates the gage pressure at which the value is calculated (atmospheric pressure = 0 bar gage pressure and the subscript 0 is used). The actual FER_p and FIR_p at each step can be calculated with Equations (5) and (6) using the actual volume of air calculated with Equation (A.3). The FER_0 and FIR_0 can change when the soil is mixed with the foam at atmospheric conditions. FER_p and FIR_p are always related to each other over the air content in the foam. When more air is incorporated during mixing FER_0 and FIR_0 will increase.

When foam bubbles are destroyed in the process FER_0 and FIR_0 will decrease. Therefore, the actual FER_0 and FIR_0 at the beginning of the test should be calculated from the used surfactant solution volume and the actual air volume in the PTC.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Theoretical relationship between pressure and foam expansion ratio (*FER*) and foam injection ratio (*FIR*) according to Boyle's gas law

Figure 2. Volumetric difference between in-situ soil, conditioned soil with a $FIR_p = 40\%$, and conditioned soil with $FIR_o = 120\%$

Figure 3. Laboratory foam generator used to produce the foam for the tests

Figure 4. Pressurized Testing Chamber (PTC) with dimensions in mm

Figure 5. Grain size distributions of the two sand soils, soil 1 and soil 2, used for the tests

Figure 1. Compression results of soil 1. Compression δ (a), void ratio e (b), pore pressure u (c), and vertical effective stress σ'_{vt} (d) plotted against the total vertical stress σ_{vt} . Filled markers represent loading, unfilled markers represent unloading, and solid lines represent the air-governed void ratio

Figure 7. Compressibility of soil 1 with different FIR_o plotted against total and effective vertical pressure. Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil and solid lines represent the air-governed compressibility

Figure 8. Compression results of soil 2. Compression δ (a), void ratio e (b), pore pressure u (c), and vertical effective stress σ'_{vt} (d) plotted against the total vertical stress σ_{vt} . Filled markers represent loading, unfilled markers represent unloading, and solid lines represent the air-governed void ratio realized if the soil would be governed by the contained air only

Figure 9. Compressibility of soil 2 with different FIR_o plotted against total and effective vertical pressure. Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil and solid lines represent the air-governed compressibility

Figure 10. Compressibility plotted against void ratio for both soils and different FIR_o s. Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil

Figure 11. Vane shear strength plotted against vertical stress for soil 1 (a and b) and soil 2 (c and d). Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil

Figure 12. Vane shear strength plotted against void ratio for soil 1 (a) and soil 2 (b). Filled markers represent void ratios below the maximum void ratio of the soil